

PULSE POLIO PROGRAMME: THE MOST EFFECTIVE SOCIAL- CAUSE MARKETING BY THE GOVERNMENT OF INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Social marketing has been a systematic application of marketing, beside other concepts and techniques, to achieve specific behavioral goals for a social good. Cause marketing or cause-related marketing is considered as a type of marketing that involve in the cooperative efforts . The term is sometimes used in more broader term and is referred to a kind of marketing effort for the benefit of social and other charitable causes. Social Cause marketing is related to marketing for a social cause i.e. related to the welfare of society, usually taken up by the Government of India in the form of various initiatives including Pulse Polio Marketing, Marketing against Dowry System, HIV AIDS Marketing, Save the Girl Child programme etc.

This study aims on “Pulse Polio Marketing” as a programme implemented by the Government of India. India reported many cases of Polio disease, few years back. But with the proper implementation of this Pulse Polio Marketing Programmes, it has been able to achieve its objective effectively. In this study, a survey was conducted on parents of the children, enquiring their opinion regarding the marketing of Pulse Polio programme and how effective it has been.

Keywords: Pulse Polio, Pulse Polio Marketing, Social Marketing, Social-Cause Marketing

INTRODUCTION

The disease has disappeared from most of the parts of the globe with the dawn of the 21st century. In all, these are 209 countries, territories and areas have succeeded in cutting down wild poliovirus cases to nil by 2003. Out of them, 134 countries have been given a certificate as polio-free countries after they have maintained zero case performance for three consecutive years.

The study attests to the need for sustaining the rigor of extensive and intensive outreach and continued engagement of the marginalized and underserved, to path down the last of India's unreached child. On taking a close look at how strategic marketing activities has resolved major attitude and behavioral barriers. The analyses will elicit new interest among partners in response to the challenges ahead.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Recent years have witnessed major changes in the way the government has marketed for the Pulse Polio Programme. Government has increased its spending all in terms of Cost, Time and People. Few studies on Marketing Programmes and strategies of the government for the Pulse Polio Programme, indicate the following:

According to a Report of CEHAT, *Gangolli (1999)* was able to explain that people's health movements and other concerned groups and movements to pressurize the government. Priorities are to be changed taking into consideration the health problems which are affecting the marginalized people and the people of vulnerable sections of the society. In late sixties, with the increasing socio-economic problems and the popularization of T.V., social ads were given increasing attention. - *Chauhan (2001)*. A report of *UNICEF (2003)* suggests, no democracies in the world have undertaken public health initiatives as monumental as India's Pulse Polio in its resolve to wipe out this disease: Poliomyelitis. The pulse Polio campaign proved to be successful. There are signs for improvement in India, one of those countries where polio is still endemic. There have been only seven cases of Polio in Uttar Pradesh to June, 2005, compared to 1200 in the same period 2002. - *Westbrook (2005)*. As per a report by *UNICEF (2007)*, A sizeable majority (73.6%) of the primary target group respondents claimed to have seen the TV

campaign of January 2007 round Pulse Polio Immunization. Among those exposed to the Polio campaign of January 2007 round, the main message that majority could recall pertaining to the need to administer polio drops to the children.

An estimated 10 million health workers and the volunteers are engaged to implement the compulsory polio Supplementary Immunization Activities (SIAs) on a recurring basis, and polio surveillance is being conducted by at least 35 000 well-trained workers . These wide sort of workers and volunteers, who are from India and also from outside, the health sector have been employed to deliver the polio vaccine during SIAs. This approach has required sustained political advocacy - *Goswami (2007)*. A carefully and well-planned public service campaign becomes a powerful weapon against drugs, social injustice, cruelty, violence, misery, diseases and social pathologies. Not to use this weapon would be a sin of neglect and indifference. Advertising is about making people see things in a different way. Public service advertising is about waking up people's good will. And good will is the moving spirit of mankind. - *Ashish (2008)*

According to a Report by *WHO and UNICEF (2009)*, Eradicating type 1 Polio from India is a major strategic objective of the Global Polio Eradication Initiative. It is due to the marketing efforts of the government that the India witnessed a surge of poliomyelitis type 1 (P1) in 2006 with as many as 648 cases, which declined to 83 in 2007. - *Yadav(2009)*.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study were as follows: -

1. Analyzing the efficiency of the marketing strategies adopted by the *Government of India* for the Pulse Polio Programme.
2. To find out which is the most contributing factor in making this campaign a success.
3. Recommending the changes that should be brought into the marketing programmes of the Pulse Polio Programme.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents, regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India, belonging to different genders.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents, regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India, belonging to different areas.

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents, regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India, belonging to different income groups.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents, regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India, belonging to different religions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sampling and Data Collection

		Frequency	proportion of sample(%)
Age	13-20	6	2.2
	21-25	24	13.5
	26-30	48	27.0
	31-35	48	27.0
	36-40	24	13.5
	41- above	28	15.7
	Total	176	100.0
Gender	m	94	52.8
	f	84	47.2
	Total	178	100.0
Aob	rural	72	40.4
	urban	106	59.5
	Total	178	100.0
Mi	0-10000	40	22.5
	10000-30000	34	19.1

	30000-50000	48	27.0
	more than 50000	48	27.0
	Total	178	100.0
Religion	hindu	114	64.0
	muslim	18	10.1
	sikh	22	12.4
	christian	10	5.6
	others	4	1.1
	secular	12	6.7
	Total	178	100.0

The present study is based on empirical analysis of efficacy of the marketing program held by government of India towards eradication of polio virus from the nation. A total of 250 questionnaires were distributed in Delhi, Noida, Ghaziabad, Faridabad and Gurgaon. 178 questionnaires were found fit for data analysis, which leads to final sample size of 178. To make the current study holistic in nature, data were collected from people of all demographic profiles as shown in table 1.

Demographic profile of respondents was analyzed using frequency distribution. Total sample size is 178. Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents.

Statistical techniques

Responses to the 53 easily understandable statements were factor analyzed. Most practiced index of internal consistency in social science researches on multi item measures, the Cronbach's alpha was computed to assess the reliability of each factor (Schmitt, 1996).

Table 2: Marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India

variable no.	Factors and Variables	Factor loadings
	Impact on social cause	
v03	Every person must be concerned about social issues (like Health Care, Family Welfare, Literacy, National Integration, etc.)	0.867
v07	Social Marketing is very helpful in social change	0.793

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v10	Social ads deliver the message properly	0.711
v14	I have acted for the social causes that interest me	0.668
v17	The presence of celebrity is the only cause to catch the people's interest in a social ad	0.609
	Effective communication/ reach by government	
v19	I think PPP is the world's biggest public health initiative programme	0.834
v20	I think that government has been able to reach the marginalized communities with a little or no access to mass media.	0.73
v25	I think that government has been able to build up strategic (customized) communication to meet new challenges upcoming with different people at different times and with different communities related to PPP.	0.667
v31	I think that government has been able to reach the mothers in the villages and urban slums, who were largely illiterate.	0.791
	Awareness by promotional activities	
v13	Social ads deliver the message properly	0.616
v22	I think that celebrities like Amitabh Bachan, Sachin Tendulkar, etc were successful in creating awareness among the public for polio eradication	0.573
v26	I think, awareness amongst the public for PPP has increased after the government has increased the promotional activities for the same	0.519
v37	I think that the marketing activities have been successful to inform people about the National Immunization Day	0.603
v38	I think that the marketing activities have been successful to remind people about the National Immunization Day	0.692
v42	I think that the use of celebrities in the advertisement for PPP, has been able to convince the general public to take their child for vaccination	0.578
	Strategies undertaken	
v23	I think that there should be some different strategies to be used for educating rural people about PPP	0.663
v43	I think that government should organize Seminars and Conferences, with common public as the audience, on Pulse Polio Programme	0.61
v47	I think that degree of commitment of all involved in PPP is satisfactory	0.59
v53	There are many Social evils in our country, therefore, I think that they must also be handled with same methodology for creating awareness amongst the public as PPP	0.779
	Accuracy of the program	
v21	I think that the amount of money invested in PPP has been rightly deployed	0.645
v36	The statistics and data provided by government regarding coverage of area and children is true	0.602
V40	The process followed by people involved in PPP is in accordance with that provided by the government	0.511
v46	I think that degree of commitment of all involved in PPP is satisfactory	0.543
v48	I think that the number of members, transit teams and the supervisors for PPP are sufficient	0.506

	Societal changes	
v39	I think that the marketing activities have been successful to change parental attitude	0.789
v49	I think that PPP has aroused a need of staying healthy in common public	0.571
v52	I think that PPP has helped society to come out of its shell of ignorance	0.56

Factor analysis

To bring down the statements to a manageable level of dimensions, factor analysis using principal components method of factor extraction. The solution's KMO measure of sampling adequacy was 0.839, with measures 0.90 being considered at the highest standard. Bartlett's test of sphericity was found significant at the 0.000 level, and indicating that the assumption of multivariate normality was met (Norusis, 2004). Factor analysis of the 53 statements yielded six factors with an eigen value 1.00. Twenty-seven of the statements came into play. The procedure yielded factors with Cronbach's coefficient reliabilities ranging from 0.61 to 0.86 (above the minimum recommended 0.70 critical value) with 67 percent of variance explained (above the minimum recommended 60 percent critical value (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 2 represents the structure of each dimension and the variables constituting each dimension. The factor loading of each variable in the respective dimension is also shown in the table. Chronbach's alpha was also calculated for each factor to measure the internal consistency of the variables of the specific factor, which shows quite satisfactory results.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The respondents of different demographics do not give equal importance to all the factors. Data analysis was done in order to find out whether the opinions of respondents regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India, varies with gender, area of belonging, income or religion.

Influence of demographic factors over the opinions of respondents regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India

Gender

Table 3 ANOVA test statistic over the opinions of respondents regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India on the basis of gender.

Scrutinizing the results from the perspective of gender of the respondents revealed that, effective communication/reach, awareness about the program, strategies undertaken, accuracy of employed staff, , opinions of respondents were not found significantly different between males

	Impact on social cause	Effective communication/reach	Awareness	Strategies	Accuracy	Changes
F	6.184	5.084	0.117	1.489	2.108	5.809
Sig.	0.014	0.125	0.733	0.224	0.148	0.017

and females, while impact on social cause and changes in the society were found to differ significantly over the members of different genders. Overall, the analysis supports the null hypothesis Ho1.

Area of belonging

Table 4 ANOVA test statistic over the opinions of respondents regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India on the basis of area of belonging

	Impact on social cause	Effective communication/reach	Awareness	Strategies	Accuracy	Changes
F	3.474	0.795	0.984	0.097	1.161	2.201
Sig.	0.961	0.498	0.402	0.017	0.326	0.090

Analysing the results from the perspective of area of belonging of the respondents revealed that, impact on social cause, effective communication/reach, awareness about the program, , accuracy of employed staff and changes in the society, the opinions of respondents were not found

significantly different between people belonging to rural or urban areas. Whereas strategies undertaken was found to differ significantly over the members belonging to different area of belonging, which on the whole supports the null hypothesis Ho2.

Monthly Income

Table 5 ANOVA test statistic over the opinions of respondents regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India on the basis of monthly income of respondents

	Impact on social cause	Effective communication/reach	Awareness	Strategies	Accuracy	Changes
F	0.835	1.912	0.292	0.735	0.170	2.009
Sig.	0.477	0.130	0.831	0.533	0.916	0.115

Scrutinizing the results from the perspective of monthly income of the respondents revealed that over all the factors namely, impact on social cause, effective communication/reach, awareness about the program, strategies undertaken, accuracy of employed staff and changes in the society, the opinions of respondents were not found significantly different among the people having different monthly incomes. This supports the null hypothesis Ho3.

Religion

Table 6 ANOVA test statistic over the opinions of respondents regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India on the basis of religion

	Impact on social cause	Effective communication/reach	Awareness	Strategies	Accuracy	Changes
F	2.097	1.347	3.806	1.397	0.650	6.908
Sig.	0.048	0.247	0.003	0.028	0.662	0.000

The results from the perspective of religion of the respondents revealed that, factors such as impact on social cause, awareness about the program, strategies undertaken, and changes in the society, were found to be significantly different over the opinions of respondents belonging to various religions. While effective communication/reach and accuracy of employed staff were found not to differ significantly. Thus, the analysis suggest that the null hypothesis Ho4 should be rejected.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results indicate that respondents opinions does not show significant variation among three categories of demographic variables undertaken namely gender, area of belonging and monthly income for opinions of respondents regarding marketing efficiency of pulse polio program undertaken by government of India. The religion of respondents do matter, the sample was constituted by people belonging to different religions as hindu, muslim, sikh, Christian, etc. which implies that people belonging to different religions have significantly different opinions regarding the efficacy of marketing activities of pulse polio program. Analysis also suggests that people belonging to different demographic profiles are all together concerned about quick an complete eradication of polio virus from the country. Respondents agree to act upon the social cause as directed by the promotional activities. They confirm the fact that government has been able to make a wide reach over the country with respect to this program. The marketing activities has successfully made the people aware about the virus and its impacts, with a majority of people interested in healthily participating in the cause. There have been a few loopholes that have been opined by few respondents regarding the presentation of false facts and figures and some of inaccuracies of policies and the staff employed. Removing these shortcomings, would make the pulse polio program's marketing a most effective and efficient one.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Hence, it may be suggested that the marketers must approach with specifically fit strategies to the people of different religions. The promotion through health staff should be more intensified. The number of visits per home should be increased so as to cover all the parents and children, especially those parents who are working and are available at their respective homes at some specific time only. The government should start the promoting the social cause using the

Interactive Media like Social Networking websites such as Facebook, Orkut, Twitter, LinkedIn etc, so as to create more awareness amongst the youth for the pulse polio programme. A database related to children and their parents should be prepared and the government should also take the initiative of Mobile SMS Advertising, giving information on pulse polio days. The use of celebrity endorsing should be increased in promoting the pulse polio programme, as people are more influenced by them. The government should target all the schools and teach the children as to the importance of Polio drops and as to the awareness of upcoming Polio Days.

The marketing theories and practices can be applied to dissemination of social issues in much the same or a better way as that of conventional products.

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